

Abstract 800 words

Using participatory methods to promote agroforestry in the Netherlands and the United Kingdom

Marlinde Koopmans¹, Paul J. Burgess², Andrew Dawson³, Michail Giannitsopoulos², Anil Graves²
Daniël de Jong³

¹: ILVO (Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food), Merelbeke, Belgium

²: Cranfield University, Cranfield, Bedfordshire, United Kingdom

³: Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, The Netherlands

Introduction

The climate emergency and the need to decarbonise is driving a major change in European economies including agriculture and land use. This transition requires farmers, advisors, researchers, and others in the food system to work together in new ways, and there is likely to be a significant role for agroforestry, i.e. the integration of trees with farming.

Between 2020 and 2024, the European project AGROMIX has used a participatory design approach to work with farmers in 12 locations across Europe to drive the transition to resilient and efficient land use in Europe

Method

The participatory design approach was based on the Reflexive Interactive Design approach (RIO in Dutch) (Bos et al., 2009). RIO is an approach to push significant structural change, i.e. system innovation. It is a systematic approach used to interactively design system innovations in complex and controversial contexts, reforming existing 'mainstream' agricultural systems. In AGROMIX a simplified version of this approach was implemented what will be described in a future publication. The presentation will compare the experience of a pilot group in Winthagen in the Netherlands with that of a pilot group in Bedfordshire in the United Kingdom.

Results and discussion

In Winthagen (NL), the participatory approach took place at a regional scale. In an early meeting, the group identified their objective as to support adaptation to climate change, strengthen biodiversity, improve water management, landscape aesthetics, and living quality, and at the same time ensure economic viability in the region. In Winthagen, the participatory design approach resulted in four design proposals that could, if implemented on a regional scale, support these objectives. They include: 1) a joint crop plan that guarantees the spatial distribution of different crops in the area, and 2) diverting water to verges and overflow plots via the construction of small attenuators in the road to increase water infiltration from and along roads. A third practice was 3) developing multifunctional swales that can be diversely planted for flowering, fruit, nuts, or biomass for energy and building materials, which can both support biodiversity and provide local self-harvesting opportunities. A fourth practice 4) was creating mini stone quarries through the landscape for temporary water storage during flood events. As a co-design process pilot, Winthagen has been effective in involving various stakeholders and designing novel solutions for the area. The majority of stakeholders identified the first practice to be most easily achievable, and they are now exploring how to further develop the ideas.

In Bedfordshire (UK), two initial meetings brought together farmers, researchers, land agents, and advisors from the Marston Vale area, which covers about 160 km², in November and December

2021. At these meetings, the primary challenge identified by the group was an awareness of the need to understand the net level of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from each farm, but confusion as to which GHG tool to use and a lack of expertise and time to collate the necessary data. Hence in the next stage of process, Cranfield University staff and students worked with five farmers and two GHG modelling organisations to estimate the net level of GHG emissions from five farms. Estimates were also made of the level of additional tree cover needed to enable each farm to achieve net zero GHG emissions. Although arable farms can reduce GHG emissions by improved fertilizer management, increasing tree cover is also an option to reduce emissions over the next 40 years. Although the UK study did not initially or directly focus on agroforestry, working with the immediate challenges identified by farmers has led to conversations about the increased integration of trees on farms. Hence working with the local Forest of Marston Vale Trust, at least one of the farmers has established substantial new areas of trees on their farm.

Conclusion

Based on the experiences in the pilots we see participatory design as a valuable and engaging approach to support the development of mixed farming systems such as agroforestry systems, based on the needs of the participants. When implemented on a regional level, farmers and other regional stakeholders such as land agents, farm advisors and civil servants learn and understand the potential role of agroforestry for tackling important regional challenges such as flood risk and carbon sequestration. Because the co-designed solutions address the challenges raised by the participants, they are likely to be implemented in practice.

REFERENCES

Bos, A. P., Koerkamp, P. G., Gosselink, J. M. J., & Bokma, S. (2009). Reflexive interactive design and its application in a project on sustainable dairy husbandry systems. *Outlook on AGRICULTURE*, 38(2), 137-145.